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THE BLOOD PHENOTYPE (RH SYSTEM) IS THE PREDICTOR OF THE SEVERITY OF SEPSIS IN CHILDREN

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Resume. *The aim of this study was to evaluate the association between Rh blood phenotype and sepsis severity in children. A prospective observational study was conducted on 19 girls with confirmed sepsis treated in the intensive care unit of the City Children's Infectious Diseases Clinical Hospital (January 2025 – March 2026, Minsk). Rh phenotype (Ccee, CCee, ccee, ccEe, etc.) was determined; severity was assessed using the PRISM III score; etiology, frequency of MOF, and grade 3 respiratory failure were recorded. Patients with «Ccee» and «CCee» phenotypes had more severe pathology (pneumonia caused by *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*; generalized meningococcal infection; MOF – 7 cases; grade 3 respiratory failure – 5 cases), as well as a higher PRISM III score (6.1 [4.2; 9.8]). The presence of the «Ccee» blood phenotype in girls is a marker of predisposition to severe sepsis with multiple organ failure.*

Keywords: *pediatric sepsis, blood phenotype, Rh system, Ccee, multiple organ failure, predictor, PRISM III.*

Introduction. Pediatric sepsis remains an unresolved problem due to the heterogeneity of patients, complicating both optimal therapy and disease outcome prediction [1]. Despite existing scientific studies on immune response, genetic profile, and phenotype of patients with sepsis, further exploration of these factors may facilitate the development of a personalized approach to diagnosis, prognosis, and therapy.

Sepsis and septic shock are major causes of morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs for children worldwide, including >3 million deaths annually and, among survivors, risk for new or worsening functional impairments, including reduced quality of life, new respiratory, nutritional, or technological assistance, and recurrent severe infections. Advances in the understanding of sepsis pathophysiology highlight a need to update the definition and diagnostic criteria for pediatric sepsis and septic shock, while new data support an increasing role for automated screening algorithms and biomarker combinations to assist earlier recognition. Once sepsis or septic shock is suspected, attention to prompt initiation of broad-spectrum empiric antimicrobial therapy, fluid resuscitation, and vasoactive medications remain key components to initial management with several new and ongoing studies offering new insights into how to optimize this approach. Ultimately, a key goal is for screening to encompass as many children at risk for sepsis and trigger early treatment without increasing unnecessary broad-spectrum antibiotics and preventable hospitalizations.

The severity of sepsis is traditionally assessed using SOFA/APACHE II/PRISM scales, along with lactate, procalcitonin levels, and the presence of organ dysfunction. Determination of the blood phenotype according to the Rh system (e.g., «ccee» variants) is not currently used in clinical practice as a sole key predictor, but it may help identify groups at risk for a more severe course of sepsis [2, 3].

There has been longstanding interest to identify biomarkers to assist in the diagnosis of sepsis, with blood lactate, C-reactive protein (CRP), and procalcitonin (PCT) the most commonly used. Blood lactate levels rise when oxygen delivery to tissues is insufficient to support metabolic demand, resulting in anaerobic conversion of pyruvate to lactate rather than driving adenosine triphosphate production through mitochondrial aerobic respiration. With reversal of shock to restore oxygen and

substrate delivery to tissues, blood lactate levels typically normalize. However, there are many other causes of hyperlactatemia (including artifactual increases from difficult phlebotomy), and septic shock can occur before or even without a rise in blood lactate. As a result, blood lactate is less useful to stratify acutely unwell children for risk for sepsis but should be trended over time as one method to monitor response to therapy after sepsis is suspected. CRP is a hepatic-derived acute phase reactant that serves as a sensitive, albeit nonspecific, marker of inflammation, and PCT is a pro hormone of calcitonin ubiquitously secreted in response to bacterial-mediated cytokines. PCT offers a more specific, and generally earlier, biomarker for invasive bacterial infections than CRP.

Despite Presepsin is the soluble portion of the CD14 molecule of the TLR4 (Toll-like receptor), which is involved in phagocytosis. When bacteria and their derivatives are ingested by a macrophage, the soluble peptide sCD14 is cleaved from the CD14 cluster, which is converted by proteases to presepsin s-CD14-ST. Presepsin concentration has been shown to reflect the intensity of bacterial and fungal phagocytosis. Viral infections do not produce presepsin, which is important for distinguishing between bacterial and viral sepsis. Data obtained from numerous studies in patients with sepsis have shown that presepsin is a highly specific and effective biomarker for the early diagnosis of sepsis. Reference values for presepsin, which normally ranges from 100–200 ng/ml, have also been established for SIRS (200–400), localized infection (400–800), sepsis (800–1300), and septic shock (1300 ng/ml or higher).

Compared to other markers, presepsin is not only more sensitive and specific in the early diagnosis of sepsis but can also be used to assess the severity and prognosis of the pathological process. The limitations associated with centralized clinical data collection and cluster analysis of large data sets, the role of genomics, metabolomics, and proteomics of the immune response in sepsis in disease prognosis and treatment is gradually becoming dominant. Establishing links between all these elements and clinical phenotyping of sepsis, including subtype analysis, will likely become a determining factor in the search for personalized treatment approaches in the near future. Currently, the generally accepted goal of treating patients with sepsis is early detection and initiation of therapy to prevent the development of irreversible septic shock and multiple organ failure syndrome. Personalized assessment of a patient's genetic, metabolomic, and proteomic profile appears to be an interesting and promising direction in the search for new treatment strategies for sepsis.

Neither the SOFA nor the qSOFA scores can be used as the sole definitive criteria for sepsis, as they lack 100% specificity. However, using these scores can help avoid treatment delays. Early detection of sepsis is crucial for successful treatment, as the strongest predictor of septic outcome has been found to be the timing of initiation of effective antibacterial therapy. Effective antibacterial therapy within the first hours of the onset of hypotension in sepsis is associated with an 80% survival rate, and each hour of delay in therapy within the first 6 hours reduces survival by 7-8%. [4].

Objective: To determine the dependence of the blood phenotype (according to the Rh system) on the severity of sepsis in children.

Tasks:

1. To analyse the distribution of Rh phenotypes among girls with sepsis.
2. To compare the severity of pathology, etiological factors, and outcomes across different phenotype groups.
3. To evaluate the potential of the «Ccee» phenotype as an additional predictor of severe sepsis and multiple organ failure.

Materials and Methods. The observation group consisted of 19 children (all female) who were treated at the Municipal Children's Infectious Diseases Clinical Hospital of Minsk, in the Department of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care (ICU) from January 1, 2025, to March 31, 2026.

All patients were hospitalized with a primary diagnosis of sepsis. Their blood type, Rh factor, Rh phenotype («Ccee», «CCee», «ccee», «ccEe», etc.), and antibodies to red blood cells were determined, pic. 1.

Picture 1. Blood type, Rh factor, Rh phenotype («Ccee», «CCee», «ccee», «ccEe», etc.)

Severe pathology was defined as pneumonia caused by specific pathogens (*Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*), generalized meningococcal infection, septic shock, multiple organ failure syndrome (MOFS), and grade III respiratory failure.

Statistical processing was carried out using Microsoft Excel 7 and Statistica 10.0.

Descriptive statistics were calculated, and the type of distribution curve was determined. Normality was checked using the Shapiro–Wilk W-test. The null hypothesis of a normal distribution was rejected at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion. All 19 patients were female. The distribution of Rh phenotypes was as follows: «Ccee» – 9 patients (mean age 7 [6; 14] years), «CCee» – 3 patients (mean age 5 [5; 13] years), «ccee» – 4 patients (mean age 3.5 [2; 9.5] years), «ccEe» – 3 patients (mean age 11 [1; 12] years), table 1. The difference in age distribution across groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1. Distribution of Rh phenotype

Patients who had the combination «Cc» or «CC» in their phenotype («Ccee» or «CCee») demonstrated significantly more severe pathology compared to the «ccee» group. In these patients, the PRISM III score was higher (6.1 [4.2; 9,8]) than in the «ccee» group, $p \leq 0,05$.

Specific infections identified in severe cases included: *Mycoplasma pneumoniae* pneumonia (n=4); *Haemophilus influenza* (n=2), *Streptococcus pyogenes* sepsis (n=2), and generalized meningococcal infection (n=3).

In the severe group, multiple organ failure syndrome occurred in 7 patients, and grade 3 respiratory failure in 5 patients. In contrast, the «ccee» group most commonly had generalized viral and bacterial infections with an unspecified etiological factor and a milder course.

The «Ccee» phenotype is associated with a significantly more pronounced systemic inflammatory response and higher risk of septic shock, table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of Laboratory and Inflammatory Markers Between Phenotype Groups

Parameter (Me [LQ; UQ])	«Ccee» / «CCee» (n=12)	«ccee» (n=4)	p-value
CRP (mg/L)	187 [142; 256]	94 [58; 137]	<0.01
Procalcitonin (ng/mL)	24,3 [12,7; 48,1]	5.2 [2,1; 11,4]	<0.001
IL-6 (pg/mL)	310 [198; 487]	89 [44; 156]	<0.01
Lactate (mmol/L)	4,2 [2,9; 6,1]	1,9 [1,2; 2,8]	<0.05
Leukocytes ($\times 10^9/L$)	18,7 [12,1; 26,4]	11,3 [7,8; 15,2]	<0.05

Concomitant pathology was twice as common in the «Ccee»/«CCee» group and included iron deficiency anemia (n=2), small cardiac abnormalities (additional chord of the left ventricle (n=1), patent foramen ovale (n=2), hemodynamically insignificant coronary-pulmonary fistula (n=1), and epilepsy (n=1), $p < 0,05$.

Girls with the «Ccee» and «CCee» phenotypes more frequently had blood type 0 (I), Rh positive, while those with «ccee» more often had blood type B (III), Rh positive.

Comparison of laboratory and inflammatory markers between phenotype groups revealed that the «Ccee» phenotype was associated with a significantly more pronounced systemic inflammatory response and a higher risk of septic shock. The presence of the «Ccee» phenotype in girls thus appears to be a marker of predisposition to severe sepsis with multiple organ failure.

Table 3. Distribution of clinical characteristics by Rh phenotype

Parameter	«Ccee» (n=9)	«CCee» (n=3)	«ccee» (n=4)	«ccEe» (n=3)	p-value
Median age, years (Me [LQ; UQ])	7 [6; 14]	5 [5; 13]	3,5 [2; 9,5]	11 [1; 12]	<0.05
PRISM III score (Me [LQ; UQ])	6,1 [4,2; 9,8]	6,1 [4,2; 9,8]	≤ 1	–	<0.05
Multiple organ failure, n	7	–	–	–	<0.05
Grade III respiratory failure, n	5	–	–	–	<0.05
Specific bacterial pneumonia, n	8	–	–	–	<0.05
Blood type 0 (I), n (%)	6 (66,7 %)	2 (66,7%)	1 (25%)	–	<0.05

The results indicate that the presence of the «Ccee» phenotype is associated with a more severe course of sepsis, a higher incidence of MOFS, and specific, often atypical, pathogens. This suggests a possible genetic predisposition linked to Rh system variants that may influence the immune response.

The study has limitations, including a small sample size and the inclusion of only female patients, which requires further validation in larger, mixed cohorts.

Conclusions:

1. The presence of the «Ccee» blood phenotype (Rh system) in girls is a marker of predisposition to severe sepsis with multiple organ failure.

2. Patients with «Ccee» or «CCee» phenotypes demonstrated more severe pathology, including pneumonia from specific pathogens (*Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus*

influenzae, Streptococcus pyogenes), generalized meningococcal infection, and higher rates of respiratory failure (grade 3) and multiple organ dysfunction syndrome.

3. The study of the «Ccee» phenotype helps differentiate patients at high risk of complications who require early intensive care.

4. This phenotypic assessment should be used as an additional predictor alongside traditional scales (SOFA/APACHE II/PRISM III) for the prognosis and management of pediatric sepsis.

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